

Formation and evolution of black holes

L. Z. Vilenchik, L. M. Pustynnikov

I. Introduction

A black hole today is understood as a region of space very densely filled with matter, with a total mass so large that nothing can leave it due to gravitational attraction. Black holes are found primarily in the center of galaxies and are only observed indirectly. The entropy approach to natural phenomena that we proposed earlier /1/ allows us to explain the birth of black holes without using the General Theory of Relativity or the Holographic Principle.

To do this, we define as virtual the state of an object that is not observed, i.e. in reality, as it were, does not exist, but has energy and entropy and can arise (manifest, be observed) under certain conditions that lead to a change in entropy. If an object has any measurable observable property, we call it a material object and say that it is a material entity. Both material and virtual objects are located in world space. Space, in this case, should be understood as a limitless empty container (or simply emptiness) in which these objects are located, occupy a certain position, interact, can move in any direction and demonstrate certain properties. About a part of space filled only with virtual objects, we can say that it is filled with a physical vacuum that has a certain energy. Energy is understood as a material entity that reflects the ability of virtual and material objects to do work.

In accordance with this approach (which shares the idea of the Big Bang), the world space before the “Big Bang” should be represented not as empty, but filled with a variety of virtual objects. It was infinite, homogeneous, isotropic, had energy and the maximum possible entropy, and the masses, sizes and any other characteristics of the interacting virtual objects located in it did not appear in any way, because the resultant of all forces associated with their interaction was equal to zero.

This space should not be imagined as “frozen.” It is possible for certain processes to occur in it, carrying out the interaction of virtual objects located in space. One of such processes may be the random emission of various energy quanta, such as photons, by these virtual objects. The random nature of this radiation, on the one hand, is consistent with quantum mechanics, and on the other, can be considered as a source of gravitational attraction of objects /2/.

The random nature of the emission of energy quanta by these objects and their resulting chaotic movement lead to fluctuations in their density. Apart from these insignificant reversible fluctuations in the density of virtual objects (required by quantum mechanics) and the corresponding entropy fluctuations, no processes changing its state occurred in this vacuum. But sometimes a single fluctuation or combination of fluctuations could become so strong that the previously existing organization no longer withstood and

was collapsing. At this turning point, called a special point or bifurcation point, it is fundamentally impossible to predict in which direction further development will occur: whether the state of space will remain chaotic or whether it will move to a certain level of order. In other words, as a result of some local quantum fluctuations, the vacuum density, entropy and free energy in various small regions of space can change abruptly above a certain critical value. There can be any number of such regions and bifurcations. These bifurcations occur randomly and are not coordinated with each other. After them, the World space becomes heterogeneous. A certain structure appears in it (areas with increased or decreased density of virtual matter). Accordingly, the entropy of space decreases abruptly and its free energy increases. Bifurcation, naturally, occurs locally, but in accordance with Mach's principle /3/ (which states that local physical laws are determined by the large-scale structure of the universe, and local changes occurring in space, in turn, affect the large-scale structure of the universe), it was reflected in the state of the entire world space. The state of space becomes unstable (due to an increase in its free energy) and the process of its evolution begins and, in particular, the formation of black holes begins as well. How does this happen?

As a result of the "structuring" of space (the appearance in it of areas with different densities of virtual objects), its entropy decreases (both locally and throughout space), and the resultant of the forces caused by the interaction of some of these objects ceases to be equal to zero. The mass of these objects and their other characteristics (size, electrical charges, etc.) begin to "manifest", i.e. these objects move from a virtual state to a real one. Selected directions appear in space along which forces begin to act and under their influence the movement of objects occurs. The entropy of space decreases and the free energy increases, which makes its state unstable, tending to decrease its free energy, increasing entropy and simultaneously decreasing internal energy. To implement this trend, objects, moving from a virtual state to a real one, continue to intensively emit "energy quanta", which leads to their chaotic movement (i.e. to the appearance of temperature). If we adhere to the idea of the "Big Bang", having become real, these chaotically moving objects, initially concentrated in a small region of space, where their density sharply increased as a result of fluctuations, should "scatter", thereby realizing their entropic interaction (as if experiencing "entropic repulsion", which Alan Guth called negative gravity /4/).

At the initial moment after bifurcation, the radiation of quanta towards neighboring objects becomes preferential compared to radiation into regions external to them. And objects begin to repel each other. This process continues to remain random, but with the said tilt and the presence of quantum fluctuations. Hollow regions appear in space, surrounded by regions filled more densely with real objects. Those appear as if "entropy holes" and a tendency to fill them with surrounding real objects. These holes can be considered as prototypes of black holes because they attract all material objects. Everything that these objects continue to emit when falling into such a hole remains in it, continuing to fill it. The material objects surrounding the hole do not receive any impulses from it, their radiation towards the hole becomes less, and the impulses they receive from the charges emitted objects located outside this hole continues to push them towards the hole. Those the hole that arises in this scenario becomes a black hole with properties generally recognized today, and when there are no objects left in the vicinity of such a black hole that are attracted to it more strongly

than to other objects, it begins to emit energy “charges” of various powers in order to increase its entropy (in Hawking's language /5/ the hole begins to evaporate). The described situation is realized in galaxies and mainly in their central regions.

II. A mathematical model of such formation and evolution of black holes

Let's consider a mathematical model of such formation and evolution of black holes. The filling of space with a variety of virtual and material objects allows it to be described using the well-known Fokker-Planck equation, i.e. direct Kolmogorov equation /6/. Let $Q(x)$ - density of local distribution in limited areas of space of a certain set of material objects. Then the probability flux density q the location of these objects there can be written in one-dimensional form as the sum

$$q = q_{demolition} + q_{diffusion} = UQ(x, t) - D \frac{dQ(x, t)}{dx} \quad (1)$$

and the corresponding Fokker-Planck equation for $Q(x, t)$ looks like

$$\frac{dQ(x, t)}{dt} = -U \frac{dQ(x, t)}{dx} + D \frac{d^2Q(x, t)}{dx^2} \quad (2)$$

Here X -coordinate, U - drift coefficient (i.e. coefficient of regular convective movement), D - diffusion coefficient. In this case we will assume

$$|U| \ll 1 \quad (3)$$

and then we can omit in equation (2) the term containing U .

Equation (2) describes the spatiotemporal evolution of the function $Q(x, t)$ in processes where the stochastic nature of the phenomenon is important. Further, we will limit ourselves to the region

$$t \geq 0, \quad 0 \leq x \leq l, \quad (4)$$

where l - some, generally speaking, changing quantity.

As boundary conditions for the stated problem we will use

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial x}(0, t) = 0, \quad UQ(l, t) - D \frac{\partial Q(l, t)}{\partial x} = q \quad (5)$$

The system of equations (2), (5) is open and autonomous, i.e. invariant to an arbitrary time shift.

1. The first stage of the formation of black holes

Evolution in this model (2)-(5) occurs in two stages that do not intersect in time. At the first stage, in which we denote the probability density and its flow $Q_I(x, t)$ and q_I , is fair the fellow

$$Q_I(x, 0) = 0 \quad (6)$$

In addition, we require the following inequalities

$$0 < Q_I(x, t) < 1/e \quad (7)$$

At this stage at the beginning of the process the value $Q_l(x, t)$ little enough. Therefore, the product $UQ_l(x, t)$ by virtue of (3), it is all the more small, and this term in (5) can be neglected in comparison with the second term. Then the boundary condition for (5) takes the form

$$D \frac{\partial Q_l(l, t)}{\partial x} = q_l \quad (8)$$

Those at the first stage, only diffusion into the black hole from the external environment takes place. In this case, as follows from equation (8), the probability density $Q_l(x, t)$ of material objects in a given hole increases. After some time t the value $Q_l(x, t)$ stabilizes, acquiring a maximum and almost constant value

$$Q_l(x, t) \equiv \text{constant} \quad (9)$$

In this case, the density gradient $Q_l(x, t)$ becomes negligibly small everywhere and the system reaches a quasi-static mode

$$\frac{dQ_l(x, t)}{dx} \approx 0 \quad (10)$$

To find a solution to equation (2) with the boundary and initial conditions we have specified, we apply, together with the Laplace transform /7/, finite integral transformations /8/: direct transformation

$$\langle Q_l(n, t) \rangle = \int_0^l Q_l(\xi, t) \cos \frac{\pi n}{l} \xi d\xi, \quad n=0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3... \quad (11)$$

and inverse transformation

$$Q_l(x, t) = \frac{1}{l} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \cos \frac{\pi n}{l} x \langle Q_l(n, t) \rangle \quad (12)$$

This leads to the following solution to the problem:

$$Q_l(x, t) = \frac{1}{Dl} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} (-1)^n \cos \frac{\pi n}{l} x \text{ and } e^{-\frac{\pi^2 D}{l^2} n^2 t} \quad (13)$$

In accordance with /6/, solution (13) satisfies the inequalities

$$0 < Q_l(x, t) < \frac{q_l}{Dl} \quad (14)$$

From (13) it follows that the density $Q_l(x, t)$, while remaining positive, grows with time from 0 to $\frac{q_l}{Dl}$.

For sufficiently large values t solution (12) goes to its maximum constant meaning:

$$Q_l(x, t) \approx \frac{q_l}{Dl} \quad (15)$$

Accordingly, approximation (10) also becomes valid.

The first stage of black hole development ends here: i.e. the local region of space under consideration turns out to be maximally filled with material objects.

2. Entropy changing at the first stage of black hole formation

Let's consider how the entropy of space change during this stage.

For differential entropy

$$S_I(t) = -k \int_0^l Q_I(x, t) \ln Q_I(x, t) dx \quad (16)$$

taking into account $Q_I(x, 0) = 0$ and landscapes

$$\lim_{z \rightarrow 0} (z \ln z) = 0 \quad (17)$$

we get equality

$$S_I(0) = 0 \quad (18)$$

With the using

$$\frac{dQ_I(x, t)}{dt} = D \frac{d^2 Q_I(x, t)}{dx^2}, \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{dQ_I(0, t)}{dx} = 0, \quad \frac{dQ_I(l, t)}{dt} = \frac{q_I}{D} \quad (20)$$

and by integration by parts we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dS_I(t)}{dt} &= -k \int_0^l (1 + \ln Q_I(x, t)) \frac{dQ_I(x, t)}{dt} dx = -k \int_0^l (1 + \ln Q_I(x, t)) \frac{dQ_I^2(x, t)}{dx^2} dx = \\ &= -k q_I (1 + \ln Q_I(l, t)) + kD \int_0^l \frac{1}{Q_I(x, t)} \left(\frac{dQ_I(x, t)}{dx} \right)^2 dx \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Taking (14) into account, we obtain

$$1 + \ln Q_I(l, t) < 0 \quad (22)$$

From (14) it follows that both terms in (21) are strictly positive. Thus

$$\frac{dS_I(x, t)}{dt} > 0 \quad (23)$$

Those entropy at the first stage of black hole development increases.

3. The second stage of black hole development

At the second stage of black hole development, the product $UQ_I(x, t)$ ceases to be small, the probability density and flux density take on the values $Q_2(x, t)$ and q_2 . At In this case, in equations (1), (5), the first term dominates over the second and the boundary condition (5) for $Q_2(x, t)$ takes the form

$$UQ_2(x, t) = q_2$$

That is the second stage of black hole development can be described using the following initially edge task problem.

$$\frac{dQ_2(x, t)}{dt} = D \frac{d^2 Q_2(x, t)}{dx^2} \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{dQ_2(0,t)}{dx}=0, \quad Q_2(l,t) = \frac{q_2}{IN} \quad (25)$$

$$Q_2(x,0) = 0 \quad (26)$$

Application of finite integral transformations corresponding to boundary conditions (25) /6/:
direct conversion

$$\langle Q_2(\lambda_n, t) \rangle = \int_0^l Q_2(\xi, t) \cos \lambda_n \xi d\xi \quad (27)$$

$$\lambda_n = \frac{\pi(2n-1)}{2l}, \quad n=1, 2, \dots \quad (28)$$

and reverse

$$Q_2(x, t) = \frac{1}{l} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \cos \lambda_n x \langle Q(\lambda_n, t) \rangle \quad (29)$$

together with the Laplace transform /7/ leads to the solution of problem (24)-(26)

$$Q_2(x, t) = \frac{2q_2}{UDl} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \cos \lambda_n x \sin \lambda_n l (1 - e^{-D\lambda_n^2 t}) \quad (30)$$

For sufficiently large values t , taking into account (28), the approximation is valid

$$Q_2(x, t) = \frac{4q_2}{\pi UD} \cos \frac{\pi}{2l} x (1 - e^{-D\frac{\pi^2}{4l^2} t}) \quad (31)$$

For further analysis and simplification, it is sufficient to use the average integral over X expressions (31):

$$Q_{2 \text{ cpeo}} = \frac{1}{l} \int_0^l Q_2(x, t) dx = \frac{8q_2}{\pi^2 UD} (1 - e^{-D\frac{\pi^2}{4l^2} t}) \quad (32)$$

Expression (32) represents an estimate of the loss from the considered medium-density black hole $Q_2(x, t)$ due to the drift mechanism, which in this case simulates Hawking radiation.

At this stage, the probability density and entropy in the region $0 < X < l$ decrease until the black hole completely disappears. When describing $Q_2(x, t)$ the above-mentioned property of autonomy is used.

III. Two possible scenarios for the evolution of black holes

Based on (15) and (32), the final density $Q(x, t)$ can be assessed as

$$Q(x, t) \approx \frac{q_1}{Dl} - \frac{8q_2}{\pi^2 OUT} (1 - \text{and}^{-D\frac{\pi^2}{4l^2} t}) \quad (33)$$

Information about the possible ranges of values of the quantities included in expression (33) is unknown, but according to Hawking's concept, a black hole should eventually cease to exist. In our model, this means that there must be equality

$$\frac{q_l}{Dl} - \frac{8q_2}{\pi^2 OUT} = 0 \quad (34)$$

and the adopted model shows the existence of two possible scenarios for the disappearance of a black hole:

1) If in (33) and (34) the value l constant during the entire process, then (33) turns (34) into

$$Q(x, t) = \frac{8q_2}{\pi^2 OUT} \text{ and } e^{-D\frac{\pi^2}{4l^2}t} \quad (35)$$

and at $t \rightarrow \infty$ density $Q(x, t)$ is practically cancelled, i.e. the black hole ceases to exist.

2) Size l in (33) and (34) can change. Then (33) shows that (34) must be represented as

$$Q(x, t) \approx \frac{q_l}{Dl} \text{ and } e^{-D\frac{\pi^2}{4l^2}t} \quad (36)$$

For clarity, let us examine a particular version of expression (36), putting in it

$$D\frac{\pi^2}{4} = \frac{1}{2}, \quad \frac{q_l}{D} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \quad (37)$$

Then (36) will be written as

$$Q(x, t) \approx \frac{1}{l\sqrt{2\pi}} \text{ and } e^{-\frac{(\sqrt{t}-\sqrt{0})^2}{2l^2}} \quad (38)$$

But (38) is nothing more than a normal distribution with respect to $\sqrt{t}$.

Density behavior $Q(x, t)$ at different values l And Q in expression (38) is such that at any fixed moment t observable quantity Q_2 less Q_1 ($Q_2 < Q_1$) if and only if $l_2 < l_1$. I.e., changes in Q and l are unidirectional. Obviously, solution (36) behaves the same way. Thus, the decrease in density Q and its final cancellation occurs under the influence of two mechanisms: due to an increase in time t to infinity as in (36), and due to a decrease in the value l to zero, as in (36) and (38).

V. Change in entropy during the evolution of black holes

Taking (36) as an example, we obtain

$$S(t) = -k \int_0^l Q(x, t) \ln Q(x, t) dx = -at \frac{q_l}{Dl} \text{ and } e^{-D\frac{\pi^2}{4l^2}t} \ln \left(\frac{q_l}{Dl} \text{ and } e^{-D\frac{\pi^2}{4l^2}t} \right) \quad (39)$$

From here, since

$$0 < \frac{q_l}{Dl} < 1, \quad (40)$$

Should be

$$S(0) = - at \frac{q_l}{Dl} \ln at \frac{q_l}{Dl} > 0, \quad (41)$$

which corresponds to the maximum entropy for density $Q_l(x, t)$.

Therefore, in agreement with (17) we have

$$S(\infty) = 0 \quad (42)$$

Thus, at the first stage of black hole development, differential entropy increases from zero to a maximum, and at the second stage it drops to zero.

IV. Conclusion

It is shown that the formation of black holes and their further development can be described using the well-known Fokker-Planck equation, i.e. direct Kolmogorov equation for the local distribution density of a certain set of material objects in a limited region of space.

Literature

1. L.Z.Vilenchik, "Entropic Essence of Nature", International Journal of Theoretical Physics, Group Theory, and Non-linear Optics, Volume 17, Number 4, pp. 295-307, (2017).
2. L. Z. Vilenchik, L. M. Pustyl'nikov, O. I. Zolotov, Entropic Features of Nature and their Application to Quantization of Gravity, Amazon, 2024.
3. E. Mach The Science of Mechanics; a Critical and Historical Account of its Development. LaSalle, IL: Open Court Pub. Co. LCCN 60010179 (1960). This is a reprint of the English translation by Thomas H. McCormack (first published in 1906).
4. A. Guth, The Inflationary Universe. Perseus Books, Reading, MA (1997).
5. S. Hogg, Black Holes (L) : The Reith Lectures, 2016.
6. Yu. V. Prokhorov, Yu. A. Rozanov, Probability Theory, M. Science, 1973.
7. G. Dech, Guide to the practical application of the Laplace transform, M. Nauka, 1971.
8. N. A. Martynenko, L. M. Pustyl'nikov, Finite integral transformations, M. Nauka, 1986.